

INCREASING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST AGGLOMERATIONS

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Abstract: This article examines the issues of increasing the economic efficiency of tourist agglomerations. The main directions of strengthening the economic potential of the tourism sector by effective management of tourist agglomerations, infrastructure development, implementation of innovative approaches and expansion of interregional cooperation are analyzed. Factors hindering the development of touristic agglomerations were identified in the study, and practical recommendations for their elimination were developed.

Keywords: Tourist agglomerations, economic efficiency, infrastructure, innovations, interregional cooperation, tourism development.

Introduction. Tourism is one of the rapidly developing sectors of the modern economy, and it plays an important role in the socio-economic development of countries. In recent years, the concept of tourist agglomerations has been considered as one of the main means of tourism development. Tourist agglomerations are regional units aimed at consolidating tourist potential, efficient distribution of resources and development of tourism services in areas located close to each other. Through the development of tourist agglomerations, opportunities arise not only to increase the flow of local and foreign tourists, but also to strengthen the economic potential of the regions, create new jobs and modernize the infrastructure. Also, this process is important in strengthening interregional cooperation and solving socio-economic problems. In this article, modern methods of managing tourist agglomerations, the importance of innovative approaches to increase economic efficiency, as well as issues of infrastructure development are thoroughly analyzed. In addition, the problems encountered in the development of tourist agglomerations and ways to overcome them are also covered.

The development of local handicrafts, cultural events and tourist services will make a significant contribution to the economy of the region. The regional tourism can be systematically and strategically developed by taking into account the above factors in the optimal placement. When the region is developed in the form of a tourist agglomeration, a wide range of services and opportunities are created for tourists, which increases the flow of tourists to the region. Thus,

through the effective use of natural and cultural resources in the region, the tourist potential is fully realized. This will increase the attractiveness of the region to tourists, attract the flow of investments in tourism and strengthen the local economy. Tourist agglomerations are an important factor for promoting sustainable development. This process is carried out by protecting the environment, using resources wisely and involving local people in the process of economic development. Sustainable tourism guarantees long-term development by ensuring the harmony of environmental, social and economic aspects. At the same time, it reduces environmental pollution, increases tourism-related income of local residents, and ensures efficient and long-term use of regional resources.

The theory of economic efficiency and growth of tourist agglomerations has been studied by various scientists. Paul Krugman, a Nobel laureate, analyzes the geographic location and growth of economic activity in his New Economic Geography theory.¹ It explains the process of agglomeration and examines how the concentration of economic activity in specific areas affects productivity and growth. Krugman's model is also useful in the study of tourism agglomerations, as it helps to explain regional growth and competitiveness through the clustering of economic activities. Robert Solow² Solow's growth model, developed in the 1950s, links economic growth to the factors of capital, labor, and technological development. Solow's model of economic growth can be used in the framework of touristic agglomerations, because this theory shows how economic activity can be developed by increasing resource efficiency, introducing new technologies and stimulating economic growth. In the process of writing this article, comparative analysis, mathematical analysis, and research methods were used, and its results are used as the basis of research. It used methods and techniques such as grouping, comparison, systematic approach, analysis and synthesis.

The stages of organizing tourist agglomerations in the region include several important processes. These steps require significant strategic planning and effective resource management for regional tourism development.

The first stage of analysis and research is the study of the natural, cultural and economic potential of the region. This includes the assessment of existing tourist attractions, infrastructure, service levels and local resources. Market research, research on the needs, preferences and requirements of tourists is conducted, and potential tourist flows and types are determined.

¹ EJ Malecki, in *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*, 2001

² R. Solow. A Contribution to the Theory of Economic Growth. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, Volume 70, Issue 1, February 1956, Pages 65–94, <https://doi.org/10.2307/1884513>

Competitiveness is analyzed, competitive aspects and disadvantages of the region compared to other regions are determined.

The second stage is the strategic planning stage, which defines tourism goals and strategies. Determining for what tourism purposes the region should be developed (ecotourism, cultural tourism, health tourism, etc.). In this, long-term strategies are developed. The brand of the region is created. Establishing the region as a unique tourist brand to make it known among tourists. This brand should reflect the unique aspects and cultural richness of the region. It envisages the formation of regional cooperation, the establishment of cooperative relations with regional organizations and local entrepreneurs, and the creation of clusters that contribute to the development of tourism.

The third phase, the infrastructure and services creation phase, will improve the transport and logistics infrastructure. Convenient and safe transport routes, passenger and cargo transportation services will be created for tourists. To strengthen the connections between the tourist places of the region, to build hotels, restaurants and entertainment venues, to create infrastructure that provides tourism services based on modern requirements in the region, to develop information centers and guide services, to organize tourist information centers so that tourists can easily find the necessary information for, the service of qualified guides will be launched.

The fourth stage is the marketing and advertising stage, promotion campaigns, promotes the tourism potential of the region on a large scale through digital marketing and other advertising channels. Tourist packages are developed for participation in local and international exhibitions, festivals and events. Tour packages are formulated to travel around the region and these packages include hotel, transportation and excursions. Through the development of online platforms, it is possible for tourists to order tourist services, excursions and activities of the region online.

The fifth stage is the stage of monitoring and development, analysis of the results, the number of tourists coming to the resort, their level of satisfaction, constant monitoring of the quality of services, attracting foreign investments: looking for financial sources and grants to attract local and international investments. Strengthening cooperation with the private sector, introducing innovative technologies, making the region more attractive by improving digital technologies and modern tourism services will ensure the formation of the region as a tourist agglomeration, and this process will bring great benefits to

the regional economy, increase the flow of tourists, and for the local population. creates new jobs.

Conclusion. The following conclusions and proposals were developed to increase the economic efficiency of tourist agglomerations. The development of tourist agglomerations has a direct impact on economic efficiency and improves the socio-economic status of regions. The development of infrastructure and interregional cooperation are important factors in ensuring sustainable growth in the field of tourism. By implementing innovative approaches, it is possible to increase the quality of tourist services and ensure their competitiveness. Development of effective strategies for management of tourist agglomerations and their implementation. Modernization of tourist infrastructure and introduction of modern services in the regions. Increasing tourist flows by strengthening interregional and international cooperation. Expanding partnerships between the state and the private sector and attracting investments. It is important to support the activities of the local population in the field of tourism and create opportunities for them.

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